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Project coordinator: Dr. Francisco Hernández-Ramírez

Project coordinator organization: Worldsensing SL

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Deliverable 6.1

Exploitation & Dissemination activities report - first year

A. Dissemination Level

PU **Public**

- PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
- CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

B. Document details

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Partners	Worldsensing SL
Authors	Dr. Andrea Bartoli, Dr. Francisco Hernández-Ramírez, Dr. Xavi Vilajosana, Dr. Ignasi Vilajosana, Jose Gorchs & inputs from the Engineering, Marketing and Commercial Departments.
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0. Executive Summary

The **overall goal** of Fastprk2 is to improve the current commercial version of the Fastprk product by implementing an innovative end-to-end on-street parking management system. Fastprk2 aims to **increase** Worldsensing's **market penetration** and gain a significant market share of the smart on-street parking sector, by the introduction of a certified and accurate occupancy detection system enriched with advanced services for cities and citizens offered on a **mobility platform**.

Echoing the Smart City definition set out under the European Innovation Partnership (EIP), Fastprk2 frames these ecosystems as a vision which goes beyond the technological capabilities and boosts a multidisciplinary and integrated approach in its application involving municipal stakeholders and parking operators. Hence, the project aims to bring together city officials, industry suppliers, EU policymakers, academia and the civil society to stimulate the uptake of "Smart Mobility" solutions in an effective way.

While there is no blueprint of what exactly a Smart City is or how it should work regarding mobility management, Fastprk2 seeks to provide tangible insights regarding on-street parking and mobility management to support replication by showcasing tests in real scenarios from which stakeholders draw meaningful lessons.

Another key aspect of the project is to highlight the sustainable benefits for cities in becoming 'smart' in line with the targets for the EU2020 Growth Strategy. Funded under the H2020 programme, Fastprk2 shows the environmental, economic and social benefits of integrating smart parking and mobility solutions and defining novel Intelligent Transport Services (ITS) as part of the urban environment. As such, a set of targets (**KPIs**) has been identified to monitor the **dissemination and communication** activities developed in the frame of the project.

This deliverable describes the exploitation and dissemination activities of Fastprk2 during the first period in a simplified version containing public data only. Confidential information has been explicitly removed in this version of D6.1.

The strong links of Worldsensing with industrial leaders has been crucial in spreading the project results. In this sense, Worldsensing has given talks and participated in worldwide events organized by renowned stakeholders presenting the project concept. Notably, Fastprk2 has been presented in a diverse list of events: i) **commercial trades** (i.e. *Smart City World Congress 2016 and the Mobile World Congress 2017*), ii) **academic initiatives** (i.e. *EAE Master in "Business Intelligence e Innovación Tecnológica 2016-2017"* and *World Smart Systems & Micro-machine Summit 2017*), and iii) **investor pitch events**).

In the second period, the project will gradually move from a technical development phase to a validation stage, in which the new product's features will be tested in real use-cases spread Europe-wide. This will allow giving a boost to **dissemination and exploitation actions during the second year** of Fastprk2.

1. Introduction

Fastprk2 is included in the “**SMEInst-10-2016-2017: Small business innovation research for Transport and Smart Cities Mobility**” topic within the H2020-SME-Instrument programme, and addresses several issues related to improving the efficiency, flexibility, safety and sustainability of today’s mobility systems in urban environments.

The dissemination and exploitation of the Fastprk2 scientific and technological results is a core aspect of the project. In this sense, the respective activities are organized in a separate work package (WP6).

This deliverable describes the exploitation and public dissemination activities that has been performed during the first period of the project (June 2016 - May 2017), and it is structured as follows: Chapter 2 overviews the project impact KPIs considering the expected and actual results as well as the accumulated deviations, Chapter 3 explains in detail the completed activities in the period and Chapter 4 presents the plan for future actions. Finally, Chapter 5 provides more details about the proposed treatment of deviations while Chapter 6 closes this document with an overview of the work performed in the frame of WP6. Additional information about communication activities is presented in the annex of this document.

2. Analysis of impact KPIs

The impact analysis of the project has been assessed through a detailed **KPIs analysis**. A set of them providing relevant, quantitative and measurable information of the project impact has been defined in the EC-GA, and they are grouped around the following five general objectives:

-Set the project's vision, scope, objectives and priorities. The KPIs in this context are:

-The % of tasks, deliverables, etc. that have been completed on time:	95%
-Number of work-shops attended:	3
-Reports from end-users:	5

-Policy impact. Continuous monitoring of policy development in Smart City clusters and activities in the European Innovation Framework. Early identification of contributions to standards.

-Number of contributions to roadmaps, discussion papers:	2
-Number of contribution to policy-makers:	2

-Visibility of the project. The visibility of the project among the industrial sectors, citizens, the media and professional actors depends on the effectiveness of the dissemination. The following KPIs have been identified:

-Number of downloads of material from the website per year:	300
-Number of registered members of the website:	50
-Number of press releases issued:	4
-Number of domain exhibitions attended:	10

-Knowledge impact creation. The impact on creation and dissemination of knowledge generated in the project depends on a high level of activity in dissemination to the proper target groups.

-Number of journal publications:	2
-Number of conference papers and presentations:	4
-Number of events attended:	10

-Impact on Europe's technology leadership. The impact from the project's technological level on the global leadership and competitiveness of Europe's industry.

-Number of business cases elaborated:	3
-Participation to venture capitals and business angels' events:	3

An overview of the expected KPI values for the whole project against those attained in the first period are shown below. Actions to be fully developed during the second year are indicated in blue.

KPIs realization during the first period is **in agreement with the plan** envisaged in the EC-GA. KPIs showing minor deviations are expected to be corrected during the second period of Fastprk2.

Activities and impact KPIs				
1-Project's vision, scope, objectives and priorities				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
1.1-The % of tasks, deliverables completed on time	95	100	105%	As planned
1.2-Number of work-shops attended	3	3	100%	Completed
1.3-Reports from end-users	5	0	0%	Second period (pilot stage)
2-Policy impact				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
2.1-Number of contributions to roadmaps, discussion papers	2	1	50%	As planned
2.2-Number of contribution to policy-makers	2	1	50%	As planned
3-Visibility of the project				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
3.1-Number of downloads of material from the website per year	300	-	0%	Functionality still not active
3.2-Number of registered members of the website	50	30	60%	As planned
3.3-Number of press releases issued	4	4	100%	As planned
3.4-Number of domain exhibitions attended	10	3	30%	Corrected in period 2
4-Knowledge impact creation				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
4.1-Number of journal publications	2	0	0%	Second period (real data)
4.2-Number of conference papers and presentations	4	3	75%	As planned
4.3-Number of events attended	10	3	30%	Corrected in period 2
5-Impact on Europe's technology leadership				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
5.1-Number of business cases elaborated	3	1	33%	Period 2
5.2-Participation to venture capitals and business angels' events	3	3	100%	Completed

3. Successful impact activities

In this section, the details that supports the KPIs realization are given providing evidence of the performed activities.

3.1 Documentation delivery

Action	Comments
1.1- The % of tasks, deliverables, etc. that have been completed on time	Fastprk2 reporting has been fully completed in agreement with the EC-GA provisions

3.2 Work-shops attended

Action	Comments
1.2- Number of work-shops attended	Fastprk2 team has attended three workshops . For the second year, the aim is to increase the involvement of engineers on key technical issues of the project such as AI and <i>Machine Learning</i>

When?	Where?	Why?
December 2016	AMEC, Barcelona (VirtuWind workshop)	Marketing plan / Business Development

When?	Where?	Why?
April 2017	Geneve, SIXSQ venue	Orchestration of IoT devices and Cloud computing platform

When?	Where?	Why?
July 2017	Crete, FORTH venue	Cybersecurity for OT and IoT devices

3.3 Contribution to road-map

Action	Comments
2.1-Number of contributions to roadmaps, discussion papers	Worldsensing has started a collaboration with the Mobility Department of Barcelona to develop of the city's mobility roadmap

During the first quarter of 2017, Worldsensing has started a two-way collaboration with the Department of Mobility of the Barcelona Council to define and adjust the mobility road-map of the city. The goal is to create ecosystems of Internet of Things (IoT) in Barcelona; this will be done by establishing a concrete link between IoT platforms and creating markets for services and applications linked to the mobility vertical. The motivation is the need to overcome entry barriers on the market to developers and service providers, due to the fragmentation of IoT platforms, as well as the creation of specific know-how behind the potentialities of Big Data algorithms.

On one hand, Worldsensing is providing traffic detectors installed in the existing infrastructure to monitor speed and other related parameters, parking sensors and the know-how regarding mobility data treatment acquired throughout Fasprk2. On the other hand, the Department of Mobility of the Barcelona City Council provides access to other mobility data of the city.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	Agreement on city roadmap regarding mobility services

3.4 Contribution to policy-maker

Action	Comments
2.2-Number of contribution to policy-makers	Collaboration with Buckinghamshire County Council and Interdigital Ltd. about the use of open mobility data

Worldsensing attended the “Transport Data Initiative (TDI)” to support the Buckinghamshire County Council (UK) policies definition about the use of open data. The TDI is led by local authorities who believe that improving the way they collect, store, and use data will help to deliver improved transport services while reducing costs. Founded by a consortium of local authorities led by Buckinghamshire County Council in 2016, the TDI has fast established itself as a major player in UK transport with representatives from over 40 different transport authorities, covering 70% of the UK population.

Supported by an extensive network of transport specialists from the wider public sector and industry, TDI enables local authorities of all sizes and budgets to benefit from innovative solutions traditionally reserved for large urban centres. With focus on the common transport challenges faced by all local authorities, TDI facilitates deep and targeted collaboration across the sector, by helping solution providers design services which meet the unique requirements of local authorities, and improving awareness within local authorities of the capacities of the wider marketplace.

When?	Where?	Why?
March 2017	Manchester (UK)	Discussion about open data use policies related to improve mobility service

3.5 Number of web users

Action	Comments
3.2-Number of registered members of the website	The website of the project does not possess the necessary functionality to register members to avoid a dual communication channel with stakeholders. Registered users are controlled through the Worldsensing main site.

The Fastprk2 public website is an important tool for disseminating the project work and results to the general audience. The design, setup and continuous update of the website is done by the marketing experts of the company, considering contributions and updates provided by the rest of the colleagues.

The project website was developed and activated immediately after the official beginning of the project, and it will remain active for at least two years after the end.

In terms of contents, the website includes relevant public information and details about the dissemination activities. New content is added as the project progresses.

More specifically, the following information is publicly available through the website:

- **Worldsensing:** general introduction to the SME;
- **Job offer:** list of Fastprk2 open positions;
- **Contact:** contact information to the project coordinator and the company;
- **The project:** a high-level overview of the project concept. It outlines the steps of the project roughly following the organization in technical work packages;
- **Executive team:** key staff involved of the project;
- **Resources:** list of deliverables as they become available for publication;
- **News:** events related to the project. Dissemination actions, announcements of paper publications, talks, tutorials and workshops related to Fastprk2 are some of the events covered here.

The project web site uses **Freecounterstat** to record metrics on users and page views.

Freecounterstat provides information of users and new sessions per month from the launch of the project web site in May/June 2016. In total, there have been more than **2300 visits** to the site by **455 different users** (*65 new users per month*).

Drilling further into the available statistics, the site has been accessed by users from **35 different countries**. The figure below shows, using colour intensities, the origin of the visitors; the distribution across the world map shows that the site has attracted most interest in Europe (Spain and UK, 313 & 23 visits respectively) with some accesses from the United States (12) and South America.

The pattern of activity is explained by the fact that project is not yet widely known outside Europe and the H2020 community. This is expected to change when tangible results are available during the second period.

3.6 Press releases

Action	Comments
3.3-Number of press releases issued	The marketing team of Fastprk2 has worked to increase the awareness of the project among stakeholders.

The public press releases of Fastprk2 have been:

Title	Date	Link
NEW FUNDING: WORLDSENSING STARTS FASTPRK2 PROJECT	1/06/2016	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2016/06/01/worldsensing-starts-fastprk2-project/
THE FUTURE SMART PARKING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	15/06/2016	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2016/06/15/great-support-center2/
NARROWBAND-IOT AT MOBILE WORLD CONGRESS 2017	27/02/2017	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2017/02/27/narrowband-iot-mobile-world-congress-2017/
INNOVATION: "INNOVATIVE IOT TECHNOLOGY FOR THE XII BUSINESS CONGRESS AT UNIVERSITY OF BARCELONA"	15/05/2017	http://www.worldsensing.com/news/innovation-innovative-iot-technology-xii-business-congress-university-barcelona/

3.7 Domain exhibitions

Action	Comments
3.4-Number of domain exhibitions attended	Fastprk2 is a strategic project for the future Worldsensing. This is the main reason why Fastprk2 has been presented at International events.

The first event attended by Worldsensing has been the “Smart City Expo World Congress 2016” (SCEWC - <http://www.smartcityexpo.com/en/>), which is an international summit of discussion about the link between urban reality and technological revolution. Some facts about the 2016 edition:

SCEWC’16: 16,688 visitors, 105 countries, 420 speaker, 591 exhibitors, 600 cities

Worldsensing is a strong supporter of Digital Revolution and Innovative Technology implementation; it has participated in SCEWC 2016 to introduce the product portfolio to possible clients and show the road-map of the EU project where it is involved. In this context, the Fastprk2 project was presented to more than 50 experts that were asking about IoT-technology and advanced high computing platform.

When?	Where?	Why?
November 2016	Barcelona (Spain)	Smart City International Congress about innovative technology

The second event has been the “Mobile World Congress 2017” (<https://www.mobileworldcongress.com/>), which is a combination of the world’s largest exhibition for the mobile industry and a conference featuring prominent executives representing mobile operators, device manufacturers, technology providers, vendors and content owners from all across the world. The event, initially named as “GSM World Congress” and later renamed as “3GSM World Congress”, is still often referred as 3GSM or 3GSM World. Some features about the 2017 edition:

Mobile World Congress’17: more than 108,000 attendants, professionals from 208 countries and 3,500 media members.

Regarding Fastprk2 exhibition, Worldsensing has collaborated with Telefonica to show a demo of NB-IoT technology.

When?	Where?	Why?
February 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	Innovative technology interconnected with mobile network

The third event has been the “IPI Conference & Expo 2017” (IPI - <http://ipiconference.parking.org>). Such event brings together more than 3,000 parking professionals from 35+ countries around the globe, representing every level of experience and segment of the parking and transportation industry. It delivers four days of exceptional education, the largest display of parking-specific technology and innovations, dozens of diverse networking chances, and the opportunity to connect with a global community. The IPI Conference & Expo provides the opportunity to develop both professional and personal skill sets offering the latest in technology; mobility and alternative transportation; enforcement, finance, and auditing curriculums; planning, design, and construction sessions; personal development and communications courses. In such a scenario, Worldsensing aimed to identify potential clients for Fastprk2 “under development” parking technology.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2017	New Orleans (USA)	Cybersecurity for OT and IoT technologies

Moreover, future events where Fastprk2 will be presented are (2nd period):

Gitex Technology Week 2017 (Dubai);
Smart City World Congress 2017 (Barcelona);
ITS-Europe congress 2017 (Strasbourg);
Mobile World Congress 2018 (Barcelona);
Intertraffic 2018 (Amsterdam)

The aforementioned list is not exhaustive neither complete; more events will be added by the commercial team of Worldsensing.

3.8 Conference paper and presentation

Action	Comments
4.2-Number of conference papers and presentations	This dissemination aspect will be pushed in the second period. The marketing team of Fasprk2 is already working to increase the activity level especially for key events in 2017/18.

When?	Where?	Why?
October 2016	Bonn (Germany)	NB-IoT in Fastprk2 sensor

When?	Where?	Why?
October 2016	Barcelona and Madrid (Spain)	NB-IoT in Fastprk2 sensor

In December 2016, Fastprk2 project was presented at the "Master in Business Intelligence and Technological Innovation" as example of future technology development for Business Intelligence in Smart mobility systems. This programme is designed for new graduates who are embarking on the initial stages of their professional careers and want to work in the fields of ICT and Business Intelligence. To this end, the program is underpinned by a clear synergy between technology and management, enabling participants to develop the skills and techniques required in Business Intelligence and Technological Innovation to thus head information technology projects in various sectors of the economy.

When?	Where?	Why?
December 2016	Barcelona (Spain)	BI tools for Fastprk2 platform and services

Finally, the engineering team of Fastprk2 is working to submit technical publication on well-known journals such as:

IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems and Transportation Research IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology	ELSEVIER Journal on Transport Policy JITS – Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems EJOR – European Journal of Operational Research ANNALS of Operation Research
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3.9 Events attended

Action	Comments
4.3-Number of events attended	Considering the transversal topics covered by Fastprk2, the attended events have covered several areas of innovation: from pure technology to "ideathon" designed to identify opportunities in the field of mobility services.

The first event where Worldsensing has presented Fastprk2 project is the “23rd World Smart Systems & Micromachine Summit 2017” (MMS 2017), formerly named World Micro-machine Summit. This edition was held in Barcelona, Spain, in May 2017. The MMS 2017 was organized by the Iberian Delegation where Worldsensing was included as innovative SME.

Fastprk2 was presented during this event since the special interest topic for this edition was **Micro and Nano systems for Smart Cities applications**. After the presentation, a roundtable was organized and the several experts asked about the new node sensing strategy, smart data algorithms and related business model.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	Worldsensing presented Fastprk2 project to European experts on physics and smart systems. A delegate from the European Commission was present at the event

The second event where Worldsensing has presented Fastprk2 project was the “XII Business Congress organized by the University of Barcelona” in May 2017. Worldsensing, a global leader in wireless sensor networks and Operational Intelligence, is strongly committed to promoting new talent. As a sponsor of the Business Congress, Worldsensing presented its innovation activities to highly-skilled and young students from the Faculty of Physics. During the event, Worldsensing presented its research and development projects in which the company is currently involved with special emphasis on Fastprk2, the cornerstone of future smart parking solutions in Europe. This helped raise awareness about how the H2020 project can help make Europe more competitive in the future. The detailed presentation of the Fastprk2 project attracted a high interest due to the major challenge it represents in different fields of application. In fact, students of mathematics were attracted by the strategy to select and implement algorithms suitable enough to process data and develop advanced services of the Fastprk2 solution.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	Worldsensing presented Fastprk2 project to new talents at the University of Barcelona

The third event where Worldsensing will present Fastprk2 project is the **Ideathon** organized by Interdigital through oneTRANSPORT project (<http://onetransport.uk.net/>). oneTRANSPORT project is an open, standards based approach to improve the mobility system implemented for Smart Cities, and it is unlocking a new generation of Smart City benefits. Within oneTRANSPORT isolated and inaccessible data from the real-time operations of towns and cities across the UK is being published into an open, standards-based infrastructure. Innovative organisations are accessing this information to provide new insights, improve decisions and build intelligent services that significantly improve citizen quality of life.

The ideathon event will bring together authorities and solution vendors to innovate in a way that regional needs are effectively addressed, while offering a new distribution channel for fast adoption of products at national and international scales. The preparatory work has been done during the first period of Fastprk2.

When?	Where?	Why?
June 2017	London (UK)	For the ideathon, Worldsensing is looking for solutions that can use or benefit from a combination of multiple traffic datasets offered through an open platform

3.10 Business cases

Action	Comments
5.1-Number of business cases elaborated	The exploitation business cases will be included in the second-year exploitation report. In this document, a preliminary analysis of the work done is presented.

The information about the Business Cases of Fastprk2 is considered confidential

3.11 Investors pitch

Action	Comments
5.2-Participation to venture capitals and business angels' events	Worldsensing is currently in the final stages of closing a Series B round of investment

The information about the Business Cases of Fastprk2 is considered confidential

4. Action plan for future activities

In this section, those “low-performance” impact KPIs, which are still under development and thus cannot be presented with concrete results in this yearly report, are introduced including action plans to correct them if necessary.

4.1 Reports from end-users

Action	Current Evaluation	Expected evaluation after one year	Comments
1.3-Reports from end-users	Low	Low	End-users reports are expected after the technology testing stage. Reports will be ready by the end of 2017

To properly validate Fastprk2 project outcomes, the following pilots will be evaluated:

1. Commercial area;
2. Residential area and;
3. Special event parking management.

The expected results must be robust and able to improve the parking management capabilities within the specific experimentations' conditions. Moreover, additional analysis will be conducted to understand how the specific solutions can be generalized on an optimized and holistic one. Such analysis will be particularly interesting to show the tool capabilities to accomplish with general requirements and at the same time be reliable to specific needs. All the results of these pilots will be collected on a specific report that will be distributed to Workdsensing's network of end-users.

Details about the pilots is considered confidential

4.2 Download material at web-site

Action	Comments
3.1-Number of downloads of material from the website per year	The project's downloadable material will be available soon within the website thus the number of events will increase in the next months.

A list of interesting materials is ready to be public. In the next months, Worldensing will post such documents in the website and. At the same time, the company will organize a strong marketing campaign by contacting international expert of the sector as well as potential Fastprk2 end-users and clients.

4.3 Journal publications

Action	Comments
4.1-Number of journal publications	Journal publications are typical high quality technical analysis. Considering the evolution of the technical project's results, in the next months we will present several studies for a peer-review evaluation.

Worldensing will increase the number of publications since they are an important way to disseminate and exploit the results generated. Potential publication venues include well reputed journals such as: *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology*; *ACM Transactions on Information and Systems Security*; *IEEE Transactions on Service Computing* *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*; *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*; *Springer Service Oriented Computing and Applications Journal*; *Advances in Internet of things*; etc. Furthermore, Worldensing aims to publish individual white papers, and contribute in ongoing white papers by different research forums in the digital domain.

5. Deviations

Deviation	Description	Qualification
3.1-Number of material downloads from the website per year	What: Number of material downloads from the website per year	Selection of appealing material to attract potential costumers
	Why: the “download” functionality has not been active in the website during the first period of the project due to two main reasons: i) avoid providing any advantage to competitors about the company’s strategy plan regarding smart parking technologies and ii) the dissemination materials have not been mature enough to make them public.	
	Corrective measures: Fastprk2 technology is now much more developed. During the pilots’ implementation, real data to illustrate the benefits of the solution will be available. Using them, a list of documents will be offered to the target audience in the official website of Fastprk2. Moreover, a list of third party documents will be also provided to attract potential Fastprk2 customers with state-of-art and market analysis about transport domain technologies.	
	Expected impact: despite this deviation, the proposed development plan regarding the downloadable material will be met. Worldsensing is expecting to achieve the KPI within the project’s lifetime.	
3.4-Number of domain exhibitions attended	What: Number of domain exhibitions attended	Pre-commercial activities will increase during the last six months of the project
	Why: Worldsensing is currently commercializing Fastprk. To avoid risking this year sales and minimize confusion between the two versions of the smart parking product (Fastprk: on sale today, Fastprk2: available in 2018), the company has decided to increase the attendances to domain expeditions worldwide during the last six months of the project.	
	Corrective measures: the list of future events has already been selected.	
	Expected impact: despite this deviation, the commercial impact of Fastprk2 is not under risk since several end-users and potential clients have been contacted directly through the commercial team of Worldsensing to show them the new solution in advance.	
4.3-Number of events attended	What: number of events attended. Apart from pre-commercial activities (above deviation 3.4), Worldsensing is also planning to attend as many technical events as possible to acquire a high-quality knowledge to enrich the Fastprk2 architecture. This includes cyber-security events, academia meetings about promising technology in physical and ICT fields.	Technical events will be attended in the second year in parallel to the test validation phase of the project
	Why: the number of attended events is below the expected value since the technical team has been focused on development tasks.	
	Corrective measures: during the second year and in parallel to the test and validation phase of the project, the technical team of Fasprk2 will attend special events to guarantee that future innovations are included in the new releases of the project under development.	
	Expected impact: Worldsensing is involved in a high number of R&D activities (more than ten National and international projects), thus an intensive number of meetings with well-known technicians and experts will be organized, providing a great vision about next generation technologies (such as micro-servers, 5G, NB-IoT, etc.), which are potentially applicable in Fastprk2.	

6. Conclusion

During the first period, Fastprk2 project has focused on the technical work such as the new sensor development and the architecture implementation. Pre-commercial activities like market analysis regarding the mobility sector have been also preliminary explored. The main results of exploitation tasks are expected to flourish by the end of the project with the technical breakthroughs ready to be shown in commercial actions. Fastprk2 has however fulfilled a few achievements with respect to the initial exploitation and dissemination objectives:

- **Planning of exploitation activities:** a detailed plan including objectives and refinements of project's exploitation models (commercial exploitation, knowledge advancement, and business plan), attendance to workshops, as well as pre-commercialization activities has been completed and it will be implemented during the second period;
- **Dissemination:** Fastprk2 has contributed to the dissemination activities of Worldsensing to enhance the corporative image of the company worldwide. The company has produced marketing material and the team has attended international events to make the target audience aware about project's potentialities and opportunities;
- **End-user contacts:** the of potential customers has been updated and the most interesting have been contacted to validate Fastprk2 technology during the second period. Moreover, a specific report has been defined to quantify the benefits of this innovative solution for typical smart city and medium-size urban centre. Such reports will be completed with the support of end-users in the next months.
- **International investors:** Fastprk2 project is one of the main pillars of the strategic plan of Worldsensing for 2020. Indeed this initiative has created a consistent view on how Worldsensing is setting up the basis to increase its revenue in the next future. Such value in innovation and technical background have contributed on attracting the attention of international actors (Serie-B investment) in Worldsensing. This is a great millstone reached to the company in which the management and technical team of Fastprk2 project has actively participated.

In conclusion, the deliverable provides an insight of Fastprk2 dissemination and exploitation activities during the first period; and the commercial details here-presented are supported by the strategic roadmap of the company considering the business perspectives of Smart Park solutions. For the sake of clarity, the deviations of the proposed exploitation and dissemination tasks compared to the Grant Agreement are summarized in Section 5.

Abbreviation List

BI	Business Intelligence
EC-GA	Grant Agreement
EIP	European Innovation Partnership
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IR	Infra Red
IoT	Internet of Things
ITS	Intelligent Transport Services
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LPWA	Low Power Wide Area (Networks)
MaaS	Mobility as a Service
NB-IoT	Narrow Band IoT
PaaS	Product as a Service
SaaS	Service as a Service
WP	Work Package

Annex 1

To maximise the impact and relevance of project's communication activities, an analysis of the external context and project scope has been undertaken through a concrete analysis presented with more details in this Annex. Key issues to be considered in communication analysis and plan are the following:

- **Communication activities are necessary** for increasing potential markets to spread smart solutions as “on-street smart parking sensors” for reducing GHG emissions, improving local environment and quality of life as well as for boosting European economy by helping Europe Industrial sector and innovation.
- **Smart parking solutions** can reduce emissions, **increase the quality of life** and improve the **European economy**. Ecological, Social and Environmental goals can be met with common solutions.
- Project's results and Demos must be used to communicate project's solutions benefits and KPIs under the three pillars of sustainability, namely: economic, social and environmental.
- The gap between the European public administration/decision makers and high tech industry must be bridged for driving SMEs to achieve internationalization and provide the basis for economy of scale. Citizens should be included in such equation to define client-oriented technology.
- Connecting cities and industry partners to demonstrate and create markets for smart solutions. In this scenario, PPPs concepts are of interest.

1. Communication aims & objectives

The overall strategy of the communication plan aims:

- To reach and engage with the target groups for Fastprk2;
- To transfer methodological and technical know-how to mobility experts and policy makers;
- To create a wider market on Smart City, IoT and especially on-street smart parking.

The communication objectives for this project are built on and consider the project objectives. The key performance indicators outlined below will be used as measures in the project's evaluation:

1. To reach and engage with target groups;

- **E-update statistics:** using an online email dissemination tool, key statistics will be collected on number of sign ups, email delivery, open and click-through rate.
- **Web statistics:** number of visits, time spent on the website, where visitors are from, correlation between visits and newsletters, share of returning visitors.
- **Press releases:** circulation figures or estimates for magazines/newspapers.

2. Transferring methodological and technical know-how;

- Download numbers of documents.
- Participation rates at workshops and study visits.
- Evaluation forms from workshops and study visits: to be made available at all our events to gain quantitative and qualitative feedback on the project and activities.

3. Foster the replication/exploitation of the smart solutions.

- Number of started/planned replications of the smart solutions.
- Number of business partnerships set up as a direct result of the project.

2. Corporate identity

Professional designers have been contacted to create a visual identity for the project and give a consistent look and feel across all communication outputs in line with Worldsensing corporate identity. To support this work, a set of branding guidelines or style guide will be produced and made available in the private project's repository for all company's actors to be downloadable during project's implementation. Key points include:

- Visual identity (logo, Horizon2020 statement, colour palette, typography, key visuals);

<p>Commercial LOGO of Worldsensing Smart parking solution</p>	
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- Terminology (key-words, project descriptions, innovation, etc.);
- Key messages.

3. Promotional materials

A portfolio of promotional materials will be produced to increase the visibility of the project and help to create a market for the uptake of the smart solutions. All communication materials will display the EU emblem, and the acknowledgment to the H2020 funding.

- **Brochure** – it will provide an overview of the project with links for readers to find out more, and it will be written in an accessible language and produced with an eye-catching design. The structure and content will be drawn up by Worldsensing’s marketing responsible and be confirmed by the project executive group. In the initial phase of the project, this will exist as an electronic version only (PDF file).
- **Word & PowerPoint templates** - to ensure a consistent, look and feel’ across the project, Word document and PowerPoint templates have been designed. The Word.doc and PPT will be used to present deliverables at internal and external events. Both templates will be available to access by the project experts within the project’s repository.
- **Roll-up banners** – it will be developed to ensure a good level of visibility of Fastprk2 at events and communicate the key elements of the project at a glance.
- **Supporting graphical elements** – derived from the brochure and website development they will be made available on the project repository for any uses.
- **General PowerPoint presentation about the project** - a standard presentation about the project will be produced for use at local, national and international meetings and conferences. It will be structured in the following way: i) main objective, ii) specific objectives, iii) target groups, iv) approach, v) implementations, vi) DEMO, vii) contact details and web, viii) URL, ix) FP-2 Logo, etc.

<p style="text-align: center;">Fastprk2 brochure</p>	
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Fastprk2 roll-up

The poster is titled 'The Next Generation Parking Management System'. It features the fastprk2 logo and 'WORLDSENSING INNOVATION PROJECT'. The content is organized into sections: 'SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE' with icons for Sensors, Platform, and Services; 'VALUE PROPOSITION' with a graph comparing 'Current technology' and 'Fastprk2'; and 'BENEFITS' with a list of advantages. A QR code is visible at the bottom left of the poster.

4. Online engagement

Following, we present the list of online engagement tools that will be used to reach the maximum number of audience for Fastprk2 project:

Website: A project website, www.fastprk2.eu to replace the interim website, is today live (September 2016). The structure and the content of the website is integral to ensure high levels of engagement; content will be tailored to encourage two-way communication with the target audience. Core content includes: description of the project idea, executive team, resources and news. To keep visitors returning, the website will be updated including the blog posts, described below. There will also be a focus on the three solutions (or concepts) being implemented to improve city parking and mobility management, with supportive cross linking to facilitate the user journey and detailed factsheets also described below. To raise the profile of the project and increase outreach, a web linking strategy with experts' opinion (particularly related to smart mobility and cities) will take place.

Fastprk2 website

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Fastprk2 website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'WORLDSENSING', 'JOB OFFERS', and 'CONTACT'. Below that, the 'fastprk2' logo is on the left, and 'FASTPRK2: THE PROJECT', 'EXECUTIVE TEAM', 'RESOURCES', and 'NEWS' are on the right. The main content area features a large dark image of a parking lot with white lines. Overlaid on this image is the text 'An Innovative End-to-End On-Street Parking Management Approach'. Below the text are two green buttons: 'MORE' and 'WATCH VIDEO'. At the bottom center, there is a 'SCROLL DOWN' button with a downward arrow icon.

Project diary and news: The e-updates will be disseminated electronically every four months. All issues will be accessible through an updated archive on the project website. Content will be derived from the blog updates and a roundup of the latest events and news from the DEMO cities. Interested stakeholders may subscribe to a mailing list to receive an annual e-update containing the latest news from the project and upcoming events. All messages to the mailing list must either come from, or be approved by, the project’s coordinator. As part of the call for interest mailing that will be part of the website promotional pack, stakeholders were invited to opt in to receiving the project e-newsletter.

Video: Experience shows that videos are ideally suited to disseminate ideas, information and know-how in an engaging way leading to higher conversion rates than static text. Videos are also social-media-ready and social-media-friendly – easy to share and easy to understand. As such they will form part of the communications strategy, seeking to tell the story/take them on a journey and to give the personal perspective. Worldsensing will produce at least one video for each DEMO site (where they will include promotional material & one interview with the city mayor, citizen or industry partner or similar) of approximately 2-5 minutes in length. These videos should be available in English and in Spanish, with English subtitles, if needed.

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